

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D 1.2 PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (1)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
PAR	Participatory action research
DG	Driving Group
CoS	Community of Schools
NCB	National Coordinator Board
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
CDG	Gender and Diversity committee
FWT	Fieldwork Team

Executive Summary

The PAR approach is crosscutting throughout the project, affecting the four Pillars (Safe learning, Safe teaching, Safe schools and safe education). It involves people who are concerned about or affected by an issue taking a leading role in producing and using knowledge about it. Participatory Action Research (PAR) is collaborative research, education and action used to gather information to use for change on social or environmental issues.

In order to work on the PAR approach in the LET'S CARE project, two training sessions have been carried out with a total of 50 participants, including the member of the DG. In this document we will give concrete examples of activities that have been carried out, with the PAR approach, throughout the project up to the elaboration of this deliverable.

The present document gathers a toolkit proposal to apply the PAR approach in the framework of the LET'S CARE project, especially in the community building actions (WP1) and the whole development of the qualitative research (WP3). The PAR approach implies, Participatory (collaboration through participation; empowerment of participants); Action (change-real life experience, evidence in terms of different outcomes) and Research (new Knowledge, documented lessons). The toolkit is organized around 7 central themes: collaboration; Knowledge; Power; Ethics; Building theory; Action; Emotions and well-being.

Finally, a roadmap has been developed that combines actions with reflections and practical examples in order to be able to carry out a practical implementation of the RAP within the framework of the LET'S CARE project that can be evaluated.

1. Introduction

The Participatory action research (PAR) methodology is conceived within the LET'S CARE project as a cross-cutting tool, which is taken up from the very beginning of the project (WP1, Task 1.1), but it will be an action that will have repercussions on all the projects.

Participatory action research (PAR) is a research paradigm centred around involving participants as collaborators in research to enact social change. Emerging as early as the 1940s and gaining relevance during the 1970s cultural turn, PAR seeks to radically subvert the inherent power dynamic in traditional research approaches by critically assessing the participant-researcher relationship and “paying attention to ordinary people’s knowledge” (Fals-Borda, 2006). Scholars such as Swantz (2007) assert that PAR practices emerged not from one single disciplinary origin but rather through a cultural moment which acknowledges the importance of standing beside those experiencing oppression and inequality and recognising their equal partnership in knowledge production.

PAR asks reflexive questions about whose ‘voice’ matters in the research process through methodological innovation and infusing community expertise with academic tools and research methods (Kendon, Pain and Kesby, 2009, pp. 90–95). The level of involvement of research participants varies according to context, aims and project resources. That said, PAR studies share several underlying assumptions:

- Formal education is not necessary to take part in valuable research.
- Those who have lived experience of an issue or system are experts and therefore are best placed to contribute to related research.
- Involvement of non-academics in research design and production can improve research by reducing biases and bringing new insights and perspectives (Organizing Engagement, 2021).

Theoretically, participatory action research unifies and transcends social psychology, feminism, Marxism, anarchism, phenomenology, and classical theories of participation and centres the idea of science as socially constructed (Fals-Borda, 2006). It is used across a range of disciplines including Human Geography, Creative Arts Practice and Public Health and can involve both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Commonly used methods within PAR include participatory workshops, group analysis techniques and photovoice.

Key benefits of conducting PAR include the ability to incorporate the lived experience of individuals and communities within social change and thus better address community-identified concerns (Balazas & Morello-Frosch, 2017). PAR calls for a breakdown between subject and object in research, viewing those involved in research as 'thinking-feeling-persons' rather than merely 'participants'.

There are also many considerations within PAR, including the high financial and time cost (Raynor, 2019) and the reliance on strong rapport and community relationships. Building trust and rapport with community partners can result in more ethical and equitable knowledge production however

requires careful ethical negotiation and should not be pursued as a token of ‘collaboration’ or in a transactional manner.

The Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology is conceived within the LET'S CARE project as a cross-cutting tool, which is taken up from the very beginning of the project (WP1, Task 1.1), but it will be an action that will have repercussions on all the projects.

2. PAR methodology in the LET'S CARE project

The co-creation process in the LET'S CARE project is built upon two elements. On the one hand, all the **structures** foreseen in the project's Communities (DG, NCB, CoS, PMAB) plus those created without being foreseen to improve the process (Fieldwork Team). On the other hand, the co-creative processes are based on the design of **methodological spaces** (workshops, meetings, thematic meetings, etc.) to unleash PAR actions.

The process consists of preparing a starting point for the different spaces in which the idea is narrowed down, improved, discarded or a new one is proposed, until its final development and implementation. Everything is done under the PAR approach which implies, Participatory (collaboration through participation; empowerment of participants); Action (change-real life experience, evidence in terms of different outcomes) and Research (new Knowledge, documented lessons). Different degrees of involvement are expected based on the individualized needs of the participants, and the process is tailored to guarantee their access, facilitate their engagement, and promote the exchange and knowledge co-production with them. This is done in accordance with current models of capacity-building for participation (whether for children, youths or adults), that foresee power sharing at incremental degrees from partnerships, through participant involvement under the researchers' initiative and finally shared decision-making between participants and researchers (Shier, 2001; Lundi; 2007).

Co-creation within a PAR approach aims at a meaningful level of involvement in which participants have the opportunity to express their views, this expression is fostered by the design of safe environments and facilitated within the group, there are active listeners and collaboration to take appropriate action on the views expressed (Lundi, 2007). This working process, and how we applied it specifically in the LET'S CARE project (initial proposal/co-creation/PAR outcomes with intermediate or final proposal if applicable), can be seen in figure 6:

Figure 6. Co-creation process and PAR approach

The above diagram illustrates the co-creation process with a PAR approach in the project. The first point of departure is reaching the participants to identify the "ideas" or needs to be covered. At this level PAR activities would be aimed at take into account the needs of the children, to incorporate the vision of the teachers and to engage the schools and stakeholders. Based on these expressed needs, alternative solutions are proposed to be developed. For example, based on children's life stories and interviews, an Idea A to conduct participant observation with the children is presented to the different groups of the project, FWT, DG, NCB. The researchers and teachers members in those groups dialogue understand what specific actions and impacts it would involve and as a result identify limitations in its application. Once all the viewpoints and experiences have been gathered, a new solution is formally proposed: the IDEA B: SMAT is presented, discussed again, and consolidated as the best technique chosen. This process of joint reflection and coordination is applied to all the chosen techniques resulting in a better adaptation of the ethnographies to the needs of the participants and the project.

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Thanks to this process, improvements have been suggested, and techniques such as photovoice and SMAT have been proposed instead of other ethnographic techniques; thematic subcommunities have been created at the request of teachers and schools, training, and co-creation workshops for teachers in the chosen techniques have been carried out. In this way the process contributes to achieve the objectives set out in the project but with a participatory and co-creative approach. Specifically, the application of this participatory and creative process has materialized in the following PAR activities carried out up to the date of the update of this deliverable D1.2:

WP	PAR ACTIVITIES	GROUPS INVOLVED
WP1 Building up a community	Engaging CoS through participatory strategies (thematic sub-communities, co-creation workshops on qualitative techniques with children and adolescents). Developing a HUB space for participation	DG, NCB, FWT, CoS (stakeholders, teachers, partners)
WP2 Theorization and characterization	Validation of the Theoretical model: creation of an interactive validation method open to consultation and co-creation of different groups	DG, NCB, CoS, Stakeholders and experts
WP3 Data collection and analysis	Co-creation on qualitative techniques to be developed with teachers, stakeholders, students. Final proposed techniques adapted after the co-creation workshops with teachers. Elaboration of the dossiers. Planned action of return of findings for prevalidation in June 2024 (see some examples in Annex 3)	FWT, NCB, CoS and Stakeholders
WP4 Designing and developing diagnosis and intervention tools	No works performed during the 1st Reporting Period. Starting M13	
WP5 Testing, validation and uptake	No works performed during the 1st Reporting Period. Will start on M30	
WP6 Policy recommendations and advocacy.	During the first year, the channels and means for the dissemination of the LET's project have been designed, with participation in numerous events, coordination with other European projects, etc. From now on, with the second year and all the	DG, NCB, CoS, Stakeholders and experts

Dissemination, exploitation and Communication	structures of participation created, a meeting space for the participation and co-creation of the materials will be carried out	
WP7 Project management and legal and ethical challenges	This work package is transversal and all suggestions made in the co-creation processes (e.g. depending on the final qualitative technique to be developed) are adapted in the informed consents to comply with all legal data protection regulations and precepts.	DG, FWT, NCB, CoS

Table 4. PAR LET'S CARE ACTIVITIES DEVELOPED

3. PAR training actions developed in the project

The PAR methodology will be applied throughout the project, putting children and their needs at the centre of the project. To achieve this, we will use the different qualitative techniques provided for in the LET'S CARE project:

Figure 1. PAR Methodology: Children Need's Let's Care Project

PAR calls for a breakdown between subject and object in research, viewing those involved in research as 'thinking-feeling-persons' rather than merely 'participants'. In this sense, the methodology carried out in the LETS project incorporates the thoughts and feelings of students, teachers, and policy stakeholders. The ethnographies foreseen in T3.3 with NEETS and children will be developed using the following techniques:

- Photovoice (Wang & Burris, 1994) with NEETS: is a participatory research and action methodology that uses the creation of images as a tool to access the reflection of the participants. For us, it is a method of accessing the subjectivity of young people, useful for our analysis, and at the same time generating a process of self-awareness and empowerment.
- SMAT with children is a child-friendly version of a SWOT that responds to four axes of analysis and associated questions related to dreams, fears, joys and sorrows (Martínez & Velásques, 2021). SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis is a framework used to evaluate internal and external factors, as well as current and future potential. The acronym SMAT stands for the Spanish words "Sueños, Miedos, Alegrías y Tristezas" (Dreams, Fears, Joys and Sorrows).

In this way, we will inquire into those situations that make them happy and/or sad, those that make them fearful, as well as their aspirations and desires for the future. The children, in groups or individually, will write, draw or express as they wish, using the materials provided and the facilitator's guidance, their own feelings in each of the four fields.

Children have specific characteristics and needs that require us to take care of the research processes and adapt some of the tools we normally use in social research. Photovoice and SMAT are accessible to these groups because it is not intrusive, they do not impose adult forms of dialogue, and their tools are familiar and accessible. The actions with NEETS and children foreseen in the project are of utmost importance in order to capture the first-person opinions and feelings of children and NEETS. The PAR approach is perfectly adapted to this purpose. The direct participation of children is essential to be able to take into account their opinions, needs and concerns in the first person and not only through the other key players. It is interesting to remember that these techniques also have great potential in pedagogical terms, because of its facility to create transformative and meaningful educational experiences for students.

Teachers are involved in the PAR approach in the LET'S CARE project from multiple perspectives. On the one hand, as research subjects (T3.1 and T3.2) they are the subjects of the interviews, the focus groups and the peer observation. But, in addition, they are the co-creators of the adaptation of the proposed techniques with children and NEETS, as will be seen in section 1.2.3 of this deliverable.

Finally, policy stakeholders are also involved in a dual role. On the one hand, within the PMAB and the project's stakeholder group and, on the other hand, as research subjects through the in-depth interviews planned with them in T3.1¹.

In addition, the LET'S CARE project must have a PAR approach in its interaction with all the elements that make up the LET'S CARE community:

Figure 2. Let's Care Project: Building Up a Community

¹ As of the date of the update of this deliverable, twenty-four in-depth interviews with stakeholders and policy makers have been conducted, two per planned country.

To influence real change in order to move towards a model of Safe Schools, Safe Learning, Safe Schools and Safe Learning:

Figure 3. Summary model of the impact of social inequality and attachment on educational opportunities (left). LETS CARE concept for creating the theoretical and practical Safe Education framework (right)

It is necessary to apply the objectives of the PAR methodology in the educational community, putting the needs of children at the center, it is intended to achieve greater knowledge from the participation and empowerment of the people involved (teachers, families, children, etc.):

Figure 3. PAR Methodology goals

3.1.1st training session June 13, 2023

The training session was held on June 13 from 10:00 to 11:30 (CET) and was attended by all 14 partners, all DG members attended. A total of 29 people participated in the training session, including 19 women and 10 men.

Figure 4. Participants by sex. 1st training session June 13, 2023

The agenda for the meeting was:

Table 1. Agenda 1st training session June 13, 2023

TASKS	TIME
Opening exercise: some initial questions	(10 min)
Explanation of PAR theory and practice	(20 min)
Practical application examples	(10 min)
Collective reflection exercise on the application of PRA in LETS CARE	(30 min)
Questions and concerns	(10 min)

The methodology of the session was eminently participative, in Annexes I and II you can see different materials produced in the session (padlet, recommended audiovisual videos).

The objective of this first session was to understand the PAR perspective in order to be able to apply it methodologically to the different areas and phases of the LET'S CARE project.

In order to achieve this objective, the following questions were discussed during the session²:

- What does the acronym PAR sound like to you? If it doesn't ring a bell: what do you think it refers to?
- What do you know about the PAR perspective?
- Have you ever implemented the PAR perspective?
- What examples of experiences can you tell us about?
- What are your expectations for PAR at LET'S CARE?

3.2. 2nd training session September 19, 2023

The second training session was held on September 19 from 10:00 to 11:30 (CET) and was attended by all 14 partners. A total of 21 people participated in the training session, including 19 women and 2 men.

Figure 5. Participants by sex 2nd training session September 19, 2023

² The full presentation and materials of the session are available [here](#)

The agenda for the meeting was:

Table 2. Agenda 2nd training session September 19, 2023

TASKS	TIME
Some initial questions. Nuria Lores - CIDALIA	(10 min)
Explanation of PAR theory in the context of the LET'S CARE project and proposal of the PAR toolkit applied to the LET'S CARE project. Nuria Lores- CIDALIA	(30 min)
Presentation of a successful example of PAR methodology with young people: SmatchS project: Sports Organizations Matching Social Inclusion Issues co-sponsored. Bianca Carina Sandbichler University of Graz (Austria)	(20 min)
Presentation of the PAR toolkit applied to NEETS research techniques within the project: Photovoice methodology. Elvira Mateos - CIDALIA	(20 min)
Questions and concerns Additionally doubts will be resolved in each session All participants	(10 min)

The session was developed with a theoretical and practical methodology. In this second session, the team of the University of Graz (Austria) in charge of the SmachS project³, co-funded by the European Union through the ERASMUS+ call for proposals, was invited to see the practical application and results of the PAR approach in a project with young people. Following the principles of complementarity and creation of synergies between European projects.

The objective of the second session⁴ was to apply the PAR theory already seen in a practical way to the LET'S CARE project, being able to offer common tools to the project partners for its implementation.

³<https://smatchproject.wixsite.com/smatchs?fbclid=IwAR0tNUTQGNQ26pBIXVcmo7BaXZZcNgKQhznanzNS7E73FaFefM7WE6qKxI0>

⁴ The full presentation of the session and materials are available [here](#)

3.3. Conclusions derived from the training sessions

The final results of both training sessions allowed to identify general issues:

- The PAR approach is a necessary approach to take into account the opinion of the different actors involved in the projects and to be able to carry out the co-creation of the results obtained as well as their appropriation.
- Dissemination, advocacy and policy action are being developed by the creation of specific infrastructure involving relevant stakeholders at the local, national and international levels (public authorities, policy makers, NGOs/Civil Society, school teachers, school leaders, students, parents' associations- and academic, institutions) and supported by carefully designed co-creation and collaboration mechanisms.
- The actions with NEETS and children foreseen in the project are of utmost importance in order to capture the first-person opinions and feelings of children and NEETS. The PAR approach is perfectly adapted to this purpose.
- Providing training on these approaches to all project partners facilitates implementation and collective learning in order to achieve better results. The interest in these sessions is evidenced by the participation in both training sessions.
- From actions to facts. By means of these theoretical and practical actions, what is foreseen in the formulation is carried out in theoretical terms and contributes to a better appropriation and understanding of the project.

4. LET'S CARE PAR Toolkit

This section includes the PAR toolkit document on the LET's project that was provided to the partners after the two training sessions.

The document is composed of an introduction where it is briefly presented what is the RAP approach and what general actions are contemplated by this approach. Subsequently, an application of the PAR approach to the LET's project is included. It then systematizes, around 7 central themes, the main issues to be taken into account for a correct application of the PAR approach to the LET's project. Finally, a roadmap is proposed for the next year for the implementation of the PAR approach in the LET'S project by the partners, which will be the basis on which the evaluation and the necessary adjustments will be made next year to improve the implementation of the PAR approach in the project for the third (2025) and fourth (2026) year of implementation.

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is collaborative research, education and action used to gather information to use for change on social or environmental issues. It involves people who are

concerned about or affected by an issue taking a leading role in producing and using knowledge about it. Many names are now used to describe research processes that are in some way 'participatory': e.g. Participatory Appraisal, Participatory Learning and Action, Community-Based Participatory Research.

The objective of the LET'S CARE PAR Toolkit is to provide guidance on how to introduce the PAR approach transversally in the different actions of the project as well as to raise the questions that we will have to ask ourselves throughout the development of the project.

PAR is a research approach, not a method. Many different methods can be used in PAR projects, as in the case of LET'S CARE: focus groups, semi-structured in-depth interviews, life stories, storytelling, photo elicitation, etc.

As explained above, the PAR approach should be oriented to these actions:

- Participatory
 - Collaboration through participation
 - Empowerment of participants
- Action
 - Change-real life experience
 - Evidenced in terms of different outcomes
- Research
 - New Knowledge
 - Documented lessons

Therefore, a PAR project involves a recurrent process of Planning, Action, Reflection and Evaluation:

Figure 6. PAR Process

In order to establish a common framework for the PAR approach in the LET'S CARE project, we present below some common questions that will allow us to keep the PAR methodology in mind throughout all the actions we carry out in the framework of the LET'S CARE project. We have organized the questions around 7 central themes⁵. These issues are a checklist for partners to consider when designing and implementing their activities under a PAR approach. These questions will form part of an online questionnaire that will be provided to partners on an annual basis in order to allow us to measure the impact and application of the PAR approach longitudinally throughout the project. It is a check list that has a triple function of planning (before any activity is carried out), monitoring (action-reflection) and evaluation (annual by means of an online questionnaire):

1. Collaboration

- Who will be involved in conducting this research?
- What roles will they have?
- Do we need to invite outside experts?
- What principles will we agree on in working together?

⁵ Adapted from Pain, Whitman, & Milledge (2019)

- How will we work? For example, how frequently do we need to meet, and what will we do between meetings?
- Who will we facilitate meetings with?
- How will we plan the details of the research? for example, we used the '5Ws' that can be useful as a way of organising decision-making actions to be taken:
 - WHAT will be done?
 - WHO will be involved?
 - WHERE will it take place?
 - WHEN will each stage happen?
 - HOW will we do this?

2. Knowledge

- What questions are most important?
- What different kinds of knowledge are going to be important?
- What methods do we need to use to find the answers to our research questions?
- What kinds of skills will be needed? Do we have these skills among the group, or do we need to bring in other people to provide help?
- What can each person present contribute to the research process?

3. Power

- Who usually carries out research and makes decisions on issues like the ones we have identified?
- Does our research allow others (outside of the project)? The transferability of knowledge must be present at all times.
- Are those people who are facilitating and involved in the steering group representative of the wider group affected by these issues?
- Are there people who are not represented, who we need to involve in certain stages? If so, how?
- How will we conduct meetings so that everyone is listened to and nobody dominates?
- How will we deal with disagreement, be sure that we don't gloss over differences, but discuss and work through different opinions?

4. Ethics

- Do individuals (or the whole group) want to be anonymous?⁶
- How are we going to store information in a way that preserves confidentiality?
- How are we going to be accountable?
- How to record what is said and what happens during the research process, from the start?
- Who should get to see this information?
- What are the potential sorts of harm that the research might cause? How can we avoid these?
- What are the potential benefits the research might lead to? How can we maximise these?

5. Building theory

- How will we record discussions, ideas, and the development of the research?
- How will we stand back from time to time to reflect on how the research is going and what has been achieved?
- Who will be involved in analysing the findings, and will everyone understand how this was done?
- Who will be involved in interpreting what the findings mean?
- How will we plan what outputs should be produced from the research?

6. Action

- What changes are needed, according to the findings of the research – e.g. to understanding, behaviour, policy? Deciding on the implications of the research for action is a crucial stage in PAR. Occasionally, a PAR group might agree that no action is needed (for example if the findings show there isn't a problem after all; or everyone agrees that the learning that has taken place during the research is enough).
- Who will do what? Who has the time and ability to get involved in follow-up actions? What resources would help? Should the findings be shared outside of the group for this to take place? Sometimes, the findings will be used only by the group itself. Often, you may want to use them to influence others.
- How do we want to share and promote the findings of the research? There are lots of possible modes of disseminating findings, and you should decide which are most appropriate and feasible. For example: a public meeting, a report to policy-makers, a press release, a poster campaign, a

⁶ Only applicable to stakeholders and policy makers, the rest are mandated to be anonymous.

website, direct changes to practice, advocacy work, further meetings with those responsible or affected by the issue in your research.

- Who could help us to get the messages across and stimulate change?

7. Emotions and well-being

- Is the research topic something that people care passionately about, or that directly affects their well-being? Generally researchers and scientists are presumed to put their feelings to one side when conducting research. But none of us actually do. Especially when we are researching a social or environmental issue that we care about, it is normal to feel emotionally invested in research to some degree. Depending on the topic, strong feelings may be normal to feel emotionally invested in research to some degree. Depending on the topic, strong feelings may be involved and these may affect participants inside and outside the research meetings.
- How will we ensure that the space we work in is as comfortable and hospitable as possible for participants?
- How will those involved in meetings deal with negative emotions?
- Might the research affect others outside of the PAR group?
- Do we have back up strategies, such as pointing people to sources of advice for particular problems or counselling services, for participants who need them?

Finally, we offer you, as a suggestion, **the following roadmap** that we can carry out within the LET'S CARE project in terms of PAR both in the actions of building community and in the research process. The following table proposes different actions and reflections that can be developed in the next twelve months, both in terms of community building and research actions.

PHASE	ACTION IN BUILDING COMMUNITY	ACTION IN RESEARCH
Action	Establish relationships and common agenda with stakeholders Collaboratively decide on issues	Establish relationships and contact with main people to interview Collaboratively decide on issues
Reflection	Work on collaboration framework	On research design, ethics, knowledge and accountability
Action	Build relationships Identify roles and responsibilities Discuss potential outcomes	Build relationships Identify roles and responsibilities Collectively design research processes

Reflection	Working relationships and information required	On research questions, design, working relationships and information required
Action	Enable participation of all members Collaborative plan future actions	Work together to implement research and collect data Enable participation of all members Collaboratively analyse findings Collaborative plan future actions
Reflection	On working together Has participation worked? What else do we need to do?	On working together Has participation worked? What else do we need to do?
Action	Begin to work on feeding research back to all participants and plan for feedback on process and findings	Begin to work on feeding research back to all participants and plan for feedback on process and findings
Reflection	Evaluate both the action and reflection processes as a whole	Evaluate both the action and reflection processes as a whole
Action	Collective identify future actions and impacts	Collective identify future research and impacts

Table 4. PAR LET'S CARE Roadmap⁷

At the end of the next 12 months, an internal evaluation of the actions developed in the framework of the project will be carried out in order to collect a second PAR roadmap adapted on the basis of the results and lessons learned for the following years of the project (third and fourth year)

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the PAR approach is essential to incorporate the standpoints of different stakeholders involved in the LET'S CARE project and to facilitate co-creation and ownership of results. Effective dissemination, advocacy and policy action will depend on the establishment of the dedicated infrastructures involving key stakeholders at local, national and international levels.

The implementation of the PAR approach ensures alignment between objectives and results in the LET'S CARE project. The first year of the LET'S CARE project highlighted the importance of directly engaging NEETS and children to capture their opinions and emotions first-hand to generate bottom-

⁷ Adapted from Pain,R., Whitman, G. and Milledge, D. (Durham University)& Lune Rivers Trust (2010-2011). Participatory Action Participatory Action Research Toolkit: An Introduction to Using PAR as an Approach to Learning, Research and Action (2019)

up knowledge during co-creation. Training all project partners in PAR methodologies facilitated collective learning, leading to improved outcomes, and the participation and interest in the training sessions underline the value of these approaches. In addition, the use of existing European projects and practical experience promotes synergies, facilitates knowledge sharing and avoids duplication of efforts.

In order to evaluate the degree to which the PAR approach has been applied in the LET'S project, the following aspects have been developed:

- Common guidelines that apply to all partners.
- A system for evaluating and monitoring the degree of implementation.

In deliverable D1.3 PAR report scheduled for month 24, the evolution of the application of the PAR approach in the project and the results obtained through this approach will be shown.

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Annex I: Padlet training sessions PAR

How can we apply the PAR in LET'S CARE

question 1: What would have been different if LET'S CARE had started with this perspective from the beginning and how we can apply it?

- alexandradimitrova: I would have taken much more time to start, as we would not have had a previous design. (5 stars)
- Cristello Stefano: return to the participatory team the results it is so important. (5 stars)
- Aniemo: we could have another aim.
- Aniemo: We wouldn't have an attachment perspective.
- Aniemo: We would have had to involve participants in the definition of our goals and methodology. (5 stars)
- Carmen Marillo Gomez: It's difficult to apply in online format.
- Aniemo: To build the knowledge with the participants. (5 stars)
- Cristello Stefano: we can apply it easily training the teachers to understand the value of the method. Cause in Italy is not known to teachers. (5 stars)
- Aniemo: Integrating moments of feedback from participants throughout the process.
- Cristello Stefano: more attention to the person and their participation. (5 stars)
- Carmen Marillo Gomez: Direct work with the schools. (5 stars)
- Aniemo: We've had a participatory perspective from the beginning as all the partners are also stakeholders thinking together what to do.
- Cristello Stefano: I am very surprised positively. (5 stars)

question 2: what would be the other objective we should take into an account?

- Carmen Marillo Gomez: Schools like principal agents of the process.
- Aniemo: Take into account cultural, legal and linguistic differences.

question 3: implementation ideas

- mercedesa22: IMPLEMENTATION: Through an iterative process, i.e. proposing, collecting feedback, refining and reproposing.
- Cristello Stefano: communication: listening more, and eliminate our filters, listening the persons and not think about the results.
- Aniemo: Translating results in a friendly/users perspective.
- Aniemo: Making findings accessible to the community by using clear and concise language.
- Aniemo: Using some kind of forum, where participants can share their ideas regarding the project. For example, in the newsletter, allowing some space for contributions from participants.
- Aniemo: organizing open forums.
- Aniemo: Giving the opportunity to answer/ give their opinion.
- Cristello Stefano: communication: the problem is that many persons and different perspectives, different contents, we need to work only in cooperation, create a team and discuss together all the strategies, but why not to listen to the final user? ask to them not just a feedback?
- Cristello Stefano: Why not to organize children web interview and participation in video about the let's care project, i kind of web tv of children? I'm thinking to involve the children as well we are organizing a web tv in different languages made by children, anyway, it could be interesting to have their participation.
- Cristello Stefano: families love a return in practical suggestions. (5 stars)
- Cristello Stefano: General reflection in the last years in Italy families are less and less participating in the school activities. (5 stars)
- Aniemo: communication platform. It has to be flexible and interesting attractive for all the stakeholders.
- Aniemo: By avoiding technicalities.
- Aniemo: GENERAL REFLECTION: There is one limitation for PAR in Let's Care, and that is that school communities (teachers, even children) are highly institutionalised and therefore very inertial in their practices. It is key to use the right levers to mobilise participation.
- Aniemo: Not paternalizing parents, avoiding biases about parents from minority backgrounds, etc. (5 stars)
- Aniemo: The results must be open to continuous/total implementation. They should not follow a top-down model.
- Aniemo: by making open questions and accepting open answers.
- Aniemo: we would still have an attachment perspective regardless.
- mercedesa22: well...but finally someone will have to gather something and offer a consistent outcome!!
- Aniemo: Ideally, the end goal would be lasting systemic change by the communities, for the communities. (5 stars)
- Cristello Stefano: I think in let's care project we need to apply PAR in every moment, creating a flow of sharing information with all the actors and train them to PAR.
- mercedesa22: well, maybe this PAR has not compulsory be applied for ALL the phases or techniques in the project...
- Cristello Stefano: the challenge is to hook the families in being involved in PAR and make them aware of the importance of this tool and the results and their active participation avoiding any criticism. (5 stars)
- Carmen Marillo Gomez: With a kind of toolkit.
- Cristello Stefano: I agree with mercedes.

<https://padlet.com/jesumigallon/how-can-we-apply-the-par-in-let-s-care-go38i2vptvtce3jn>

D1.2 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (1)

<https://padlet.com/jesumigallon/questions-for-initial-reflection-bh66ahpec84cckrg>

Annex II: Audiovisual material PAR

Here you can watch some videos. Some of them explain the PAR perspective, to review the theoretical part. Other videos are presentations of specific projects, so that we can visualise the application of the perspective to very different contexts and objectives.

1. What is participatory action research?

Institute of Development Studies

This video provides a basic introduction to Participatory Action Research, explaining its fundamentals and principles.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ISl7JKQuxw&t=5s>

2. Participatory Action Research (PAR) with children

NIHR ARC North East and North Cumbria

An oral presentation on the methodology.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NkKN_Q1by6o:18 / 6:54

3. Pa'lante Restorative Justice: Youth Participatory Action Research (YPAR)

Pa'lante Restorative Justice

A Youth Participatory Action Research (YPAR) project where they engage in critical action research to address a problem that is relevant to their lived experience at Holyoke High School.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RJ5dHttlWRU>

4. Community Based Research In Action

An example of research and action to make a Beirut street pedestrianised, taking into account the challenge of meeting the needs of all parties.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9t88F5IHlvo>

5. Nature as pathway. A participatory action research project

A project pioneering examples in Finland of Green Care practices, nature-based activities with a social innovation purpose

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-2qL_xl8Rfs

6. Youth-Led Peacebuilding: Participatory Action Research

United States Institute of Peace

This video documents an initiative undertaken in Kenya in 2017 and 2018 and explores its utility and effectiveness as an approach for youth-led peacebuilding in marginalized communities marked by violent extremism.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pvsNeKlbbss>

7. PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH

Focus on co-generation of knowledge with community-level stakeholders in Kenya

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zekv0ouN6og>

8. Participatory Action Research (PAR) Social Mapping

POPULAR EDUCATION CONSULTANTS

In this video we can see an example of a social mapping workshop to identify the most pressing social, economic, political, police and cultural problems/needs of communities.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DPF9d5Eks8Y>

9. Participatory Action Research - Finding solutions for pastoralists to increase climate resilience

Sustainable Agriculture Tanzania

Here is another practical example of the PAR application, Farmer-Centred Research (FCRP) in Tanzania. It is a research platform that has helped farmers to obtain practical solutions to their agricultural and livestock problems.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CHyMy-rRdoE>

10. Participatory Action Research in a Fiji Context

Another example from the Fiji context

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=32ufnXCV4W8>

11. Participatory Learning and Action approaches to improve food and nutrition security in India.

D1.2 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (1)

A project to improve nutrition knowledge and hygiene among women and Anganwadi Workers in Madhya Pradesh.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EkxA-uZFo7E>

12. Health Systems Strengthening - Participatory Action Research in Guatemala

A participatory action research project in Guatemala, funded by the Director's Catalyst Fund at LSTM, that co-designed a tool for health leaders and community partners to assess and improve urban health governance (presentation)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pUSzH08Y4YA>

Annex III: Example of co-creation with teachers of qualitative tools for students⁸

jesusmigallon2 12/18/2023 ⇄

• PUGLIA

Preparazione del workshop

Definire gli obiettivi, i gruppi target, lo spazio e il tempo a disposizione per l'organizzazione del workshop.

Obiettivi

⇒ COBELLO STEFANO 12/18/23 4:50PM
bambini consapevoli dei loro disagi a scuola

🗨️ 0

⇒ COBELLO STEFANO 12/18/23 4:51PM
alunni consapevoli dei fattori di disagio a scuola

🗨️ 0

⇒ ANONYMOUS 12/18/23 4:52PM
Stare bene a scuola per stare bene sempre.

🗨️ 0

⇒ ALESSANDRAMICHIELETTO2 12/18/23 4:52PM
dare nome ad uno stato d'animo)

🗨️ 0

⇒ BRUNA TEBALDO 12/18/23 4:53PM
Creare un ambiente il piu possibile sereno e accogliente

🗨️ 0

⇒ ANONYMOUS 12/18/23 4:54PM
Bonora Katia
 Ben Essere CONDIVISO

🗨️ 0

⁸ Link to the [full document](#)

D1.2 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (1)

LETS CARE

1 Y 2 PRIMARIA	3 Y 4 PRIMARIA	5 Y 6 PRIMARIA
<p>Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz con perspectiva de género en la etapa educativa marcada</p>	<p>Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz en el estudio y comprensión de niños con movilidad reducida en la etapa educativa marcada</p>	<p>Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz con una perspectiva inclusiva con la población migrante</p>
<p>Color de ropa más usado</p>		<p>Conocer los diversos países, culturas de nuestros compañeros de clase.</p>
<p>juguetes que tienen</p>	<p>niños del cole, familiares... que hayan estado lesionados</p>	<p>Famosos que les gusten que sean personas de otro origen étnico/racializados (P.ej Vinicius)</p>
<p>profesiones</p>		<p>Comidas internacionales</p>
<p>deportes</p>	<p>fotos de calles con barreras arquitectónicas: un bordillo, escaleras...</p>	<p>Foto en la que un alumno se encuentra sólo y los demás están en sus grupos y les preguntaría</p>
<p>dibujos</p>	<p>Deportistas, famosos, etc.. de movilidad reducida que ejemplifican el esfuerzo y la lucha diaria.</p>	<p>Juegos tradicionales o populares de diferentes países.</p>
<p>madres/tías/abuelas que conozcáis que trabajen en algun area científica (Areas STEM)</p>	<p>Historias de mascotas que ayudan a personas con movilidad reducida (ONCE y otros)</p>	<p>Pulseras, ropa, detalles de otros países</p>
<p>fotos de juegos</p>		
<p>el papel de las abuelas...</p>		
<p>Fotos de objetos cotidianos: Un cucharón, una llave inglesa...</p>		
<p>quién hace qué en la familia (cocinar, comprar, colgar cuadros, hacer chapucillas en casa...)</p>		

